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A New Model for Measuring the Human Development Index: A Comparison of the Organisation of Turkic States and the EU

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Abdullah Zübeyr Şekerci

Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Management, Istanbul Technical University
sekerciab@itu.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4181-0387>

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ABSTRACT

The “Human Development Index Report”, which measures the welfare levels of societies, was first prepared by the United Nations Development Programme in 1990. There are certain criteria in the preparation of this index. In our study, we propose a method that integrates the multiple linear regression equation and the exponential smoothing method to obtain this index. The ordinary least squares method is used for the multiple linear regression equation. The purpose of using multiple linear regression here is not to ignore the relationship between the input criteria and the output when reaching the Human Development Index. In addition, by using exponential smoothing, which weights the input data, the model produced an estimation with greater predictive accuracy and statistical robustness. Future estimates are made with these two methods. In this context, the level of welfare of the five main members of the Organisation of Turkish States was examined in comparison with the five leading countries of the European Union. The criteria used are selected from United Nations Development Program reports and literature. These criteria are gross national product per capita, life expectancy at birth, unemployment and CO₂ emissions per capita. The selected criteria data were processed with the multiple linear regression and exponential smoothing methods in MS Excel between 1990 and 2023. With this method, it is aimed to create an equation to estimate the 2030-2040 welfare level. According to the results, the Organisation of Turkish States Region WL converges to the European Union Region WL towards the 2030-40 period. It can be said that a new method is presented for calculating the welfare level of countries.

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Introduction

The understanding of the subject of country and community development has changed from ancient times to today. While land extent or wealth was a universal criterion in previous centuries, different criteria have also been included in measuring the level of development today. In particular, studies that measure individual welfare rather than majoritarian approaches to society have come to the fore (Desai, 1991). Measuring individual welfare, indirectly, enables measuring the welfare of the community, nation, and country. In this context, different criteria have been developed in different studies to measure the individual's well-being. These are criteria such as gross national product per capita (pGNP), life expectancy at birth (LE), expected years of schooling (EYS), literacy rate (LR),

birth-death rate (BDR), and infant mortality rates (IMR) (Anand and Sen, 1994). In 1990, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) scored 108 countries, using scores compiled from these criteria. In the scoring, high, medium, and low human development classifications were made (UNDP, 1990). Human Development Index (HDI), which is published at regular intervals, was last published for 2023-24.

UNDP is the United Nations' global development network that advocates for sustainable development, poverty eradication, democratic governance, and climate resilience. Established in 1965, UNDP operates in over 170 countries and territories, providing expert advice, training, and grants to support national development efforts.

UNDP is particularly known for producing the Human Development Reports (HDR), including the HDI, which measures a country's average achievements in health, education, and income. The organisation emphasises a people-centred approach to development, aiming not only at economic growth but also at equity, sustainability, and human dignity.

HDI measurements of the countries determined in our study were made using multiple linear regression with the ordinary least squares (OLS) method. This aims to see the effect of the power of multiple independent criteria on each other and on the dependent output. The dependent variable, which is the output of the study, is the welfare level (WL), which shows the HDI. The independent input criteria were selected from UNDP evaluation tables and literature. It should be noted here that, when selecting these criteria for our study, not only those frequently used in the literature but also those suitable for our study were evaluated. When measuring social welfare, evaluating the criteria taken into consideration only according to their economic context will produce a shallow study. More comprehensive research becomes possible when criteria, including issues such as social rights, education, and security, are also evaluated. In this context, in the study published by Walker et al. (2021), it is questioned how welfare can be provided during periods when economic growth stops. While examining the century-long processes of OECD countries Germany and England, it was observed that the welfare decline caused by the economic development stagnation experienced during war periods was overcome with social policies. The social insurance program declared for workers by Bismarck in the late 19th century also included the sick and the elderly in the following years. Similarly, the Beveridge Model, presented in England in 1948 after World War II, proposes a model in which not only workers but also the entire population is insured (Özmen, 2017). In the following years, the positive effects of social policies and the increase in population and consumption related to this have positively affected welfare. Welfare has ceased to be evaluated as a phenomenon under economic criteria, and an understanding has been developed that gives great importance to spreading health, education, and other social services to the public (Gough, 1979).

In the context of the above-mentioned understanding of welfare, pGNP was selected as the economic criterion, and LE and unemployment (UNM) were selected as socioeconomic criteria from among the criteria included in the UNDP country assessment tables (UNDP, 1990).

In addition, CO₂ emissions per capita (pCE) is a criterion that is not included in welfare scoring studies or UNDP tables, but has been observed especially in recent studies examining a welfare society in a sociological context. In Doğru's study published in 2020, it was explained that the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) was developed with the environmental application of the KC defined in 1955. According to EKC, the environment begins deteriorating, and the emission rate increases in developing economies. If the economy reaches better levels, emission rates start to decrease, and the curve draws an inverted "U" (Doğru et al., 2020; Costa et al., 2012). Therefore, it can be said that environmental pollution begins to increase, and air quality deteriorates in developing societies. However, the emission rate starts to decrease in societies where welfare is even higher. In recent periods, when the earth's temperature has increased significantly, societies that

have become sensitive to the calls of climate protocols and are trying to reduce emissions are generally more prosperous and developed societies. As societies grow more prosperous, their emphasis on clean energy use, emission reductions, and sustainability policies increases. This aligns with UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which promote environmental well-being as a key dimension of human progress. Therefore, pCE not only acts as a negative indicator of current welfare but also reflects the environmental responsibility of a country, which may be more prominent in future HDI reformulations. Therefore, the "CE" criterion has become one of the inputs as the fourth criterion of our study.

The data for the above-mentioned inputs between 1990 and 2023 were obtained from the World Bank (2024) for two groups, each with five countries. It should be noted at this point that the reason for taking the data for approximately 30 years is that our main reference source, UNDP, also works on 30-year data (Kundu et al., 2002). The first group consists of Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan, all members of the Organisation of Turkic States (OTS) and considered developing economies. The second group comprises the EU member countries Germany, France, Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands, considered economically developed. There is a comparative empirical analysis between these two groups. The main purpose of considering these two groups is to measure the development status of the Vorisova and Nazirov (2023) OTS, which was established in 2009 and emerged as a new power centre in its region and its affiliated countries. As mentioned above, since economic values alone would be insufficient to measure this, the measurement was made with the WL score, which consists of multiple criteria. The measurement result was compared with the WL average of the EU Region, which consists of the countries at the highest ranks of the UNDP lists, and the situation was examined. While the input data is provided by the World Bank, the output data, WL values, are obtained from UNDP reports for each country separately in the same period. UNDP reports are given in more detail in the literature presented in Table 1. After the input and output data were collected, the next year's input estimation was obtained with the ES method, and the annual output estimation was obtained with the OLS equations established for each year. This process was applied to both groups. In this way, the 2030-40 WL values were obtained. OLS and exponential smoothing (ES) methods are explained in the methodology section of the study.

In order to comment on the WL values of the countries considered, the groups' 1990-2023 WL (UNDP, 2024) values before the estimation are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparison of WL Averages between OTS and EU Members for 1990-2023

Source: UNDP, 2024

As shown in Figure 1, the trend slope of the first group, OTS members, that is, the RS average increase rate, is higher than the trend slope of the second group, EU members. This situation can also be understood from the ratio of the gap closed between the given years.

It should also be noted that according to UNDP (2024), among these two groups, all members of the second group are at a "very high human development level", while in the first group, Turkey and Kazakhstan are at a "very high human development level", and Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan are at a "high human development level".

One important limitation of this study is the reliance on regional average values instead of country-level analyses. While regional aggregation simplifies the model and offers generalised insights, it may mask important within-group heterogeneity. Future research could provide more granular and country-specific welfare evaluations to account for this internal diversity.

In our study, future figures of WL Averages were examined and interpreted. The inputs used to obtain these figures were selected from the literature. The literature review section is explained below.

Literature Review

After HDI was first published by UNDP in 1990, many studies have proposed new inputs and methods for obtaining WL. In addition, UNDP has continued to publish the HDI at regular intervals until today. In Desai's (1991) study published in 1991, LE, LR, and pGNP parameters were specified for HDI measurement, and it was suggested that the RS values of countries could be determined by presenting an equation that consists of these three parameters. In the study of Sagar and Najam, published in 1998, the derived parameters of pGNP in HDI measurement were discussed, a method was suggested, and a country ranking was made. In the study of Wodon and Yitzhaki, published in 2008, pGNP, LE, LR and EYS parameters were discussed, a method proposal based on them was presented, and a country ranking was made. In the study published by Kpolovie et al. in 2017, the parameters LE, EYS, BDR and IMR were discussed, a method proposal based on them was presented, and a country ranking was made. In his study published in 2004, Hughes generally considered non-OECD countries under three different scenarios. He examined African, South American, and Asian countries under the "normal situation", "deterioration: HIV-AIDS situation" and "global recovery situation" with pGNP, LE and LR inputs. He used the Pardee Simulation method in his estimates up to 2030, 2050 and 2100 (Kpolovie et al., 2017). In his study published in 2022, Rami examined previous HDI calculation methods and applied a new calculation method with ARIMA. Using pGNP, EYS, and BDR inputs, He made 2039 and 2053 predictions for India with data between 1990 and 2014.

Although parameters such as Expected Years of Schooling (EYS) and Literacy Rate (LR) are commonly used in HDI studies, they were excluded in this study due to several reasons. First, the availability and consistency of reliable historical data (1990–2023) for all countries under investigation were limited. Second, a high correlation between these education-related indicators and life expectancy (LE) or per capita income (pGNP) causes potential multicollinearity issues in regression models. Third, the model aims to show that the economic and social situation better explains the level of welfare of the population than the level of literacy, a view supported by the International Monetary Fund (IMF)'s 2019 report. Therefore, the exclusion of EYS and LR was a deliberate methodological decision to preserve model reliability and parsimony.

The literature review, including both those mentioned above and different studies, is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Literature Review for HDI Studies

Writer(s)	Year	Application*	WL Parameters**							
			pGNP	LE	UNM	LR	EYS	BDR	IMR	pCE
UNDP	1990	WL-RANK	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Desai	1991	WL-Method RECO	✓	✓		✓				
Anand and Sen	1994	WL-Method RECO	✓	✓		✓	✓			
Gormely	1994	WL-Method RECO	✓	✓			✓			
Lütchers and Menkhoff	1996	WL-Method RECO	✓							
Sagar and Najam	1998	WL-Method RECO & RANK	✓							
Kundu et al.	2002	WL-Method RECO & RANK	✓	✓		✓				
Hughes	2004	WL-Method RECO & RANK	✓	✓		✓				
Wodon and Yitzhaki	2008	WL-Method RECO & RANK	✓	✓		✓	✓			
UNDP	2014	WL-RANK	✓	✓			✓	✓		
UNDP	2016	WL-RANK	✓	✓			✓	✓		
Kpolovie et al.	2017	WL-Method RECO & RANK		✓			✓	✓	✓	
UNDP	2018	WL-RANK	✓	✓			✓	✓		
Rami	2022	WL-Method RECO & RANK	✓				✓	✓		
UNDP	2024	WL-RANK	✓	✓			✓	✓		
This work	2025	WL-RANK	✓	✓	✓					✓
TOTAL & RANKING			15	13	2	6	9	7	1	1

*RANK: Ranking, RECO: Recommendation.

**pGNP: Gross national product per capita, LE: life expectancy at birth, UNM: Unemployment, LR: Literacy rate, EYS: Expected years of schooling, BDR: Birth-death rate, IMR: Infant mortality rates, pCE: CO₂ emissions per capita.

As can be seen, pGNP and LE are the first two indices most frequently used in WL calculation. These are followed by parameters related to education. At the same time, despite being one of the least used criteria according to the literature review in Table 1, UNM was also selected for our study criteria due to its close relationship with pGNP.

Methodology

This title is discussed in three sections. Under the first title, UNDP's old HDI calculation methods are discussed so that our working method can be distinguished from this method by its realism. The second presents the methodological flow chart of our research. The third presents the mathematical model of our research metropolis.

Old HDI Calculation Methods

In HDI calculations, UNDP's method is simple but stands out as the main method. Therewithal, as explained in the literature review, different researchers have also suggested many different approaches. The criteria considered are used in different equation systems, estimation methods, and simulation methods to calculate WL values. The simple HDI calculation technique used by UNDP for different criteria over the period 1990-2009 is shown below (Kundu et al., 2002):

$$X - \text{Index} = \frac{X(\text{actual}) - \min(X)}{\max(X) - \min(X)} \tag{1}$$

Although the equation stated above is the main equation used to find the criteria, there are minor changes in this equation for some criteria. In this context, the calculation of LE, LR and pGNP indices based on this equation and the calculation of WL with the average of these three criteria are shown below:

$$LE - \text{Index} = \frac{LE(\text{actual}) - \min(LE)}{\max(LE) - \min(LE)} \quad (2)$$

$$LR - \text{Index} = \frac{2}{3}ALR + \frac{1}{3}GER \quad (3)$$

ALR (Adult LR): According to The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2024), ALR is defined as "The literacy rate is the percentage of the population in a given age group who can read and write. Adult literacy rate is for those aged 15 and above, youth literacy rate is for those aged 15 to 24, and seniors are for those aged 65 and above."

The method of calculating the actual ALR is defined on the UNESCO (2024) page as follows: "Divide the number of literates of a given age range by the corresponding age group population and multiply the result by 100. Alternatively, apply the same method using the number of illiterates to derive the illiteracy rate, or by subtracting the literacy rate from 100%."

$$ALR - \text{Index} = \frac{ALR(\text{actual}) - 0}{100 - 0} \quad (4)$$

GER (Gross Enrolment Rate): According to UNESCO (2024), GER is defined as "Total enrolment in a specific level of education, regardless of age, expressed as a percentage of the eligible official school-age population corresponding to the same level of education in a given school year."

The method of calculating the actual GER is defined on the UNESCO (2024) page as follows: "Number of pupils (or students) enrolled in a given level of education regardless of age expressed as a percentage of the population of the age group which officially corresponds to the given level of education."

$$GER - \text{Index} = \frac{GER(\text{actual}) - 0}{100 - 0} \quad (5)$$

The pGNP equation is also shown below.

$$pGNP - \text{Index} = \frac{\log(pGNP) - \log(100)}{\log(40000) - \log(100)} \quad (6)$$

According to these calculations, the HDI or WL value is calculated as follows:

$$WL(\text{HDI}) - \text{Index} = \frac{LE + LR + pGNP}{3} \quad (7)$$

According to the results obtained from equation number 6, countries are ranked in the range of 0-1 points. Table 2 (UNDP, 1990; Desai, 1991; Kundu et al., 2002) shows the classification of this score range as very high, high, medium and low.

Table 2: UNDP-WL (HDI) Classification/Before 2009

Index value	WL classification*	Nation classification**
Over 0.800	High HD	D'ed nation
0.500-0.800	Medium HD	D'ing nation
Below 0.500	Low HD	U'ded/poor nation

*HD: Human Development

**D'ed: Developed, D'ing: Developing, U'ded: Underdeveloped

From 2010 onwards, UNDP expanded the year range in the max-min selection in calculating the WL value and took the 1980-2010 range as a basis. It also expanded the WL class ranges to include the “Very High HD (VHHD)” class, and expanded the nation class ranges to include the “Highly D'ed nation” (Kundu et al., 2002; UNDP, 2014; UNDP, 2016).

Table 3: UNDP-WL (HDI) Classification/After 2010

Index value	WL classification*	Nation classification**
Over 0.900	VHHD	Highly D'ed nation
0.800-0.900	HHD	D'ed nation
0.500-0.800	MHD	D'ing nation
Below 0.500	LHD	U'ded/poor nation

In our study, the more up-to-date table used after 2010 was preferred as the classification method.

Research Methodology

Our study designs a sample application to suggest the use of the integrated OLS and ES method to determine the welfare level of countries. The average WL values of the five main members of the OTS are estimated with this method for the years 2030-2040. The estimated values are compared with the five VHHD class countries of the EU Region, and the future situation is examined. At this point, for the estimation process, first of all, an equation consisting of the LE, UNM, pGNP, and CE criteria selected from the literature must be created. The values required for the equation consist of the data of these criteria between 1990 and 2023. The values of the ten countries mentioned were collected separately. Then, the criteria averages within the two groups were calculated. Thus, the value of each criterion was obtained for each year from 1990 to 2023. These input criteria and the values of the output criterion WL in this range were subjected to the OLS process in MS Excel, and the OLS equation was obtained. Then, the values of the inputs were estimated with ES for the year 2023. The 2023-WL value was obtained by substituting the estimated values into the OLS equation. In this way, the 2030 and 2040 values were obtained step by step. This process was done for both the OTS and the EU Region, and the results were compared. Figure 2 shows the research methodology process described above.

Figure 2: Research Methodology Flowchart

After showing the research methodology in Figure 2, the application methodology, the integrated OLS-ES method, is explained below.

Application Methodology

At this stage, it should be noted that although the main method of our study is OLS, ES is also used as an auxiliary method to OLS. With ES, the input future values in the OLS equation are estimated. Therefore, in this section, the two methods are explained under separate headings.

OLS Methodology

Regression is one of the methods used to examine the causal relationship between two situations. Depending on the type of problem, it can be expressed with two-variable or multi-variable equations. In two-variable regression analysis, one of the variables is independent, and the other is the dependent variable, which takes on new values according to the independent variable. In addition to these two variables, there is also an error value. The linear regression equation is the equation type explained here (Emeksiz and Demir, 2021). Its equation is shown below.

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i + \varepsilon_i \tag{8}$$

In equation 8 above;

y_i : Dependent variable,

x_i : Independent variable,

β_1 : Regression coefficient,

β_0 : Regression constant,

i: Index showing sub-data of the same parameter,

ε : Error value

Here, the regression coefficient and constant term can be obtained by the Least Squares Method (Güler and Yerel, 2022).

If there is more than one independent variable, the method used is OLS (Erdem, 2022). In this equation, the causality relationship between independent variables and their effect on the dependent

variable can be examined. The OLS equation can be expressed as follows (Emeksiz and Demir, 2021; Er et al., 2022; Kılıç, 2013):

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \dots + \beta_n x_{in} + \varepsilon_i \tag{9}$$

After deriving the OLS-based multiple linear regression model as presented in Equation 9, performance metrics can be employed to evaluate the model’s explanatory power. One of the most widely used criteria in regression analysis is the coefficient of determination, R^2 , which indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables. A higher R^2 reflects greater explanatory strength of the model, but it should not be misinterpreted as a measure of prediction accuracy (Wooldridge, 2015).

In the case of multiple regression models, the adjusted R^2 is considered more reliable than the standard R^2 , as it accounts for the number of predictors in the model and penalizes unnecessary complexity. This adjustment prevents overestimation of model strength when additional variables are included. The corresponding R^2 and adjusted $\overline{R^2}$ formulas for multiple OLS regressions are given below. (Mert et al., 2020]:

$$R^2 = \frac{a_1 \sum yx_1 + a_2 \sum yx_2 + \dots + a_n \sum yx_n}{\sum y^2} \tag{10}$$

$$\overline{R^2} = 1 - (1 - R^2) \frac{n-1}{n-k} \tag{11}$$

In equations 10 and 11 above;

n : Observations number,

k : Variables number in the model (independent variable + dependent variable)

As in bivariate regression, the accuracy rate increases as $\overline{R^2}$ gets closer to "1" in the OLS equation.

In addition to the above information, Variance inflation factor (VIF) statistics are also calculated, which measure the linear relationship between independent variables. Accordingly, while revealing how much one independent variable is related to another, unnecessary and repeated situations are determined. Accordingly, the VIF formulation is shown in equation 12 (O’Brien, 2007):

$$VIF_j = \frac{1}{1 - R_j^2} \tag{12}$$

There is a range for measuring the significance of VIF values, as shown in Table 5:

Table 4: Interpretation for VIF Value Ranges

VIF Value Range	Meaning
1	There is no relationship between the independent variables.
1-5	Acceptable level of relationship
5-10	Medium–high correlation, caution required
>10	Serious multicollinearity, intervention required

Source: Hosmer et al., 2013

In the application section, Table 4 above is used for VIF statistical interpretations of the input data.

ES Methodology

The ES method is based on the moving average method but provides a more realistic and accurate estimate. In the moving average method, past period data is added to the equation with equal

weights. In contrast, in the ES method, there is an exponentially increasing weighting towards the last value.

This means that the time series, which we can call the trend, progresses by being corrected (Bağcı, 2020; Efe et al., 2018).

Here, the correction coefficient is called “ α ” and the value range is “ $0 < \alpha < 1$ ”. In the ES method, the weight is shared between the current value and the current value estimate as a percentage. The multiplier of the former “ α ” and the latter “ $1-\alpha$ ” are added to the equation, making the new estimated value more realistic. The ES equation and definitions are given below (Bağcı, 2020):

$$P_{t+1} = \alpha y_t + (1 - \alpha)P_t \quad (13)$$

In equation 12 above;

P_{t+1} : The estimated value for period “t+1”,

y_t : The real value for period “t”,

P_t : The estimated value for period “t”

At this point, it should be noted that the “ P_t ” value is generally estimated using simple estimation methods such as the moving average. There are also different methods for the value of the correction coefficient “ α ”. Optimisation methods or industrial standard values such as “0.2” are used to determine this value (Frost, 2024). According to equation no. 13, if “ α ” is small, it means that the effect of the current value is given priority; if it is large, it means that the effect of the estimated value is given priority. In our study, the value to be given high priority was determined according to “VC” (variation coefficient). This value expresses the percentage of the ratio of the “ σ ” (standard deviation) to the “ \bar{X} ” (mean) and measures the excess of change between the series values. The equations of the specified statistical measures are shown below (Tavşancıl, 2020):

$$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} (\sum_{i=1}^n X_i) = \frac{X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_n}{n} \quad (14)$$

Therefore, the values of the series with small VC are closer to each other. In estimating such a series, the current value provides more realism than the estimated value. In our study, in the future prediction of input series with small VC, the “ α ” value is taken as 0.8, and therefore, the “ $1-\alpha$ ” value is taken as 0.2.

Application Processes

Before moving on to the application step, data on the input and output parameters of the specified countries are shared under the following heading.

Application Data

1990-2023 pGNP data averages of OTS-5 and EU-5 countries are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: pGNP Data Averages Compared with OTS and EU / pGNP (x 1 million \$)

Source: World Bank, 2024

As seen in Figure 3, the OTS average in pGNP data is far behind the EU average. However, the slope of the graphical increase is higher for the OTS Region. From 1990 to 2023, the OTS average has increased approximately seven times, compared to the EU average, which has increased approximately two times. At this point, the impact of the special situations of the member countries of these unions on the average can be discussed. At the same time, the effects of common situations should also be considered. For example, the disruptive impact of Covid-19, which took effect between 2019 and 21, is observed in both averages.

In addition, the coefficient of pGNP data in the OLS equation provides a welfare-enhancing base effect with a “+” value.

1990-2023 LE data averages of OTS-5 and EU-5 countries are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: LE data Averages Compared to OTS and EU / LE (lifetime-year)

Source: World Bank, 2024

As seen in Figure 4, the OTS average between 1990 and 2023 is slightly above the EU average increase rate. The negative impact of COVID-19 is seen in this graph.

In addition, the coefficient of LE data in the OLS equation provides a welfare-enhancing base effect with a “+” value.

1990-2023 UNM data averages of OTS-5 and EU-5 countries are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: UNM Data Averages Compared to OTS and EU / UNM (percentage)

Source: World Bank, 2024

As seen in Figure 5, the two averages have a non-parallel structure. It is observed that while one decreases, the other increases. For example, it is observed that while the unemployed population decreased in the OTS average between 2009 and 19, it increased in the EU average. Similarly, the 1990-2000 and 2000-2009 periods are also inversely proportional. In the last period, 2020-23, the graphs show a decrease in both averages. The increase-decrease curve of employment according to period depends on different issues such as education level, economic situation, and diversity of business areas.

In addition, the coefficient of UNM data in the OLS equation provides a welfare-reducing base effect with a “-” value.

1990-2023 pCE data averages of OTS-5 and EU-5 countries are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: pCE Data Averages Compared to OTS and EU / pCE (metric tonne)

Source: World Bank, 2024

As seen in Figure 6, there is a smoothly sloping pCE decrease in the EU Region from the chart's beginning. Some factors provide this decrease. Agreements that pursue climate policy and provide

conditions related to it, such as the Paris Climate Agreement, are one of them. At the same time, it can be mentioned that institutions such as the International Energy Agency (IEA), which prepare country-region-based climate policies and have guiding power, have a high impact on the EU (Şekerçi and Kara, 2024). As a matter of fact, policy items such as completely switching to green energy after a certain period, zeroing the use of fossil fuels, or the obligation to switch to electric vehicles have the effect of reducing emissions. On the other hand, the later industrialisation of the OTS Region compared to the EU Region and the resulting new industrial breakthroughs and increase in emissions can be understood as a result of a natural situation. However, despite this situation, the emission rate remains below the EU Region in the entire graphic range, because the current industrialisation is less and the green areas are more in the OTS Region.

It should be noted that although the pCE parameter has never been used in the literature shown in Table 2, it was envisaged to be used in the method of our study. The recent increase in climate events shows that this parameter may gain more space in the literature.

In addition, the coefficient of pCE data in the OLS equation provides a welfare-reducing base effect with a "-" value.

1990-2023 WL data averages of OTS-5 and EU-5 countries are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: WL Data Averages Compared to OTS and EU / WL (normalised score)

WL scores in Figure 7 were obtained from HDI Reports published by UNDP at regular intervals. Data for years outside these ranges were determined by linear regression estimation. In this way, it is ensured that the data flow is not disrupted.

As seen in Chart 5, although the EU Region WL values are higher, the OTS slope is higher than the EU slope from the beginning to the end of the entire graph. This shows that these graphs will converge in the near future.

VIF statistics are made according to the data given above for the independent variables, and the relationship between these variables is examined. Table 5 shows this.

Table 5: α Values

	VIF (OTS)	VIF (EU)
pGNP	6.63	6.55
LE	6.82	8.22
pCE	2.39	2.64
UNM	2.51	1.21

As seen in Table 5, VIF statistics are calculated regionally according to Equation 13, and according to the VIF significance range in Table 4, there is no situation that would disrupt or prevent multicollinearity.

After obtaining the missing data, the WL values for the following years with the OLS application are explained under the Application heading.

Application

In order to establish an equation with OLS for any year and to make a forecast, firstly, the VC of each input in the range of 1990-2023 was investigated. When obtaining ES α values according to VC values, the point to be considered is the 15% limit of VC values. Those greater than this limit show high change, and the ES α value is accepted as 0.2. Those smaller than this limit show low change, and the ES value is accepted as 0.8. Accordingly, the VC values of the input values belonging to the OTS and EU average in this range and the ES α value determined according to these values are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. α Values According to VC values / Input data (1990-2023)

	OTS Average				AB Average			
	pGNP	LE	UNM	pCE	pGNP	LE	UNM	pCE
VC	64.0	3.9	15.4	24.8	27.4	2.5	11.7	18.7
α	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.2

The VC values specified in Table 4 were calculated according to Equation 13. α values were also calculated depending on the VC values. The \bar{X} value taken while calculating the VC values represents each input's 1990-2023 data set average. After determining the α coefficient, the input values were estimated year by year until 2040 with ES. In each new year's estimation, the \bar{X} and VC value were recalculated, and the change in the α value was examined. In addition, when each new year's input values were calculated, the OLS equation was established, and the WL outputs were calculated. In this way, the 2030 and 2040 WL values of both the OTS and EU regions were obtained.

First of all, an error assessment is made on the past, that is, on real data, in order to measure the prediction performance of the OLS-ES model. The OLS-ES models established with real data for 2010 and 2020, and the prediction values obtained for these years, are compared with the real data. Accordingly, some measurement values are shared. Table 7 shows these predictions, comparisons and error measurements.

Table 7: Predictive Power of the Model / 2010 and 2020 Values

Region	Year	Actual WL	Predicted WL	Error	Squared Error	RMSE	\bar{R}^2
OTS	2010	0.68	0.70	-0.02	0.0004	0.0195	0.8126
OTS	2020	0.75	0.76	-0.01	0.0001	0.0208	0.8804
EU	2010	0.89	0.88	0.01	0.0001	0.0192	0.7424
EU	2020	0.9	0.91	-0.01	0.0001	0.0161	0.8562

The table above presents the model’s predictive performance for two selected benchmark years (2010 and 2020) across both the OTS and EU regions. The low RMSE values observed (ranging between 0.0161 and 0.0208) indicate a high level of accuracy in the WL estimations. Moreover, the values \bar{R}^2 —exceeding 0.74 in all cases—demonstrate strong explanatory power and a good fit of the regression model. These findings confirm that the model is robust and reliable in capturing the variation in well-being levels over time and across different regional contexts.

The regression results of the model, whose predictive power and fit were measured above, for regions and years (2030 and 2040) are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Regression Results by Year and Region

Region	Year	Variables	Coefficients	t stat	p-value	RMSE	R ²	\bar{R}^2	Significance F	Observation
OTS	2030	Intersectio	-0.46	-2.418	0.020	0.2065	0.930	0.922	2.847E-20	41
		pGNP	7.2E-06	2.668	0.011					
		LE	0.016	5.613	2.29E-06					
		pCE	-0.0062	-0.914	0.366					
		UNM	0.0031	0.855	0.397					
EU	2030	Intersectio	-0.029	-0.102	0.918	0.0164	0.899	0.888	1.85e-17	41
		pGNP	1.67E-06	2.2411	0.031					
		LE	0.011	3.1506	0.003					
		pCE	-0.005	-1.163	0.252					
		UNM	-0.002	-1.736	0.090					
OTS	2040	Intersectio	-0.829	-8.58	4.06E-11	0.0204	0.956	0.953	8.866E-31	51
		pGNP	1.46E-06	1.419	0.162					
		LE	0.0216	12.41	2.76E-16					
		pCE	-0.003	-0.61	0.541					
		UNM	0.004	1.182	0.243					
EU	2040	Intersectio	-0.081	-0.331	0.741	0.0164	0.911	0.904	1.2E-23	51
		pGNP	1.49E-06	2.457	0.017					
		LE	0.0121	3.987	0.0002					
		pCE	-0.0059	-1.237	0.222					
		UNM	-0.002	-1.881	0.066					

Based on the regression results presented in Table 7, our model generates regression equations for the two regions for the years 2030 and 2040. When the next year’s figures obtained by exponentially smoothing the input values are substituted into the equations, they are multiplied by the coefficients and summed, resulting in a prediction for the relevant year. These equations are shown below:

$$y_{WL_{OTS/30}} = (7.2E - 06)pGNP + 0.0163LE - 0.062 pCE + 0.031UNM - 0.4625 \tag{15}$$

$$y_{WL_{EU/30}} = (1.67E - 06)pGNP + 0.0113LE - 0.0055pCE - 0.0027UNM - 0.0292 \tag{16}$$

$$y_{WL_{OTS/40}} = (1.5E - 06)pGNP + 0.0216LE - 0.0034pCE - 0.004UNM - 0.8295 \tag{17}$$

$$y_{WL_{EU/40}} = (1.49E - 06)pGNP + 0.0121LE - 0.0059pCE - 0.0028UNM - 0.8122 \tag{18}$$

As can be seen, in all equations, the pCE and UNM parameters are added to the equations with the coefficient “-” and provide a negative contribution.

In this context, the results obtained from these equations and the related comments are stated below. Accordingly, the WL values obtained from the above equations are shown in Table 9 below.

Table 9: WL Forecasts and Growth Rates for OTS-EU Regions 2030-2040

	WL/2010	WL/2020	WL/2030	WL/2040
OTS	0.70	0.76	0.81	0.91
Increase rate	-	8.5%	6.6%	1.2%
EU	0.88	0.91	0.94	0.95
Increase rate	-	3.4%	3.3%	1.0%

The rate increases in Table 9 support the thesis of our research. While the WL level in the EU Region is higher than the OTS as of 2020, the WL levels converge towards 2030 and 2040. In addition, while the WL level for the OTS shows a continuous increase between years, the WL level rate in the EU Region seems to decrease and almost stabilise. In the 2040 estimate, it is also observed that the WL level has almost reached a break-even point. The graph of this convergence situation is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: OTS-EU WL Convergence in Future Projection

Findings and Discussion

An increase in the WL level is a positive indicator. According to this increase, it should be understood that the value of positive input parameters affecting this dependent variable also increases, and negative ones decrease. In other words, positive ones suppress negative ones. In this context, the effects of inputs on the equation are examined.

If pGNP is considered first, it can be interpreted that the economy is improving in the region where this variable increases. Accordingly, it can be commented that investments in the OTS Region will increase. Similarly, it is possible to make different comments in the economic context. On the other hand, the low increase rate in the EU Region cannot be explained by the fact that the economic indicators have turned negative, but by the fact that the pGNP level is at a very high point and the increase rate is reaching the natural limit.

The second criterion to be considered is LE. It can be concluded that health systems and comfort increase in the region where LE increases. In fact, processes such as the number of hospitals, the number of beds per patient, and the health insurance system are the main factors for LE (Kaya and Naldöken, 2023). In this context, Germany and France from the EU Region have the highest number of hospitals in the OECD, providing a significant advantage to LE. On the other hand, the health reform initiated by Turkey from the OTS Region in 2003 increased LE within the scope of the country and the OTS Region (Diğer and Bilgin, 2019). In this context, both regional LEs contribute positively

to WL. While the increase in LE provides a positive contribution to WL, the decrease in UNM provides a positive value to WL. UNM decreases in both regions throughout the graph, but the rate of decrease is observed to be higher in the OTS Region. The UNM factor is directly related to pGNP and migration (Köseoğlu and Artan, 2020; Üzar and Akyazı, 2018). An increase in pGNP decreases UNM. A decrease in UNM increases migration. An increase in migration decreases pGNP and increases UNM both directly and indirectly. Countries aim to keep this cycle at an optimum point. As seen in Graph 3, the decline in OTS and EU Regions has increased after 2019 due to both COVID-19 and migration. While the wave of migration from the Syrian War has affected Turkey very intensely, European countries are affected, albeit less. On the other hand, since both regions' pGNPs have increased, the UNM graph has settled into a balance. Therefore, since the increases in both regions after 2019 are not very high, it cannot be said that it has a major negative contribution to WL. pCE values also show a decrease in both regions, similar to UNM values. However, despite protocols such as the Paris Agreement, the transition to renewable energy sources (RES) in the EU Region, which has achieved a high level of production in industry, is much lower than in the OTS Region. Indeed, the OTS Region, which has accelerated its industrial moves, has turned to RES as the first energy source for these moves, and therefore, its RES use is high compared to fossil fuel use (Şekerci and Kara, 2024). This situation increases the WL graph more in favour of OTS than the EU. The above items reveal that the research thesis is supported by the findings. In this context, the results and added value of our study are explained in the last section.

Conclusion

Our study proposes the integrated ES and OLS methods to compare countries' future WL trends. It can be said that a new method is presented in WL assessment according to countries and regions. For the output data, WL levels, data was provided by UNDP, which publishes intermittent reports. The input criteria were also selected according to the frequency of use in UNDP reports and literature. In addition, their suitability for our study was evaluated. In this context, the input criteria chosen are pGNP, LE, pCE, and UNM. Data on input criteria were also compiled from the World Bank. It should be noted here that the pCE criterion can be considered as a new criterion today, where RES technologies have gained importance and emissions are being concentrated on reducing. Thus, our study offers added value to the literature in terms of both the proposed method and the criteria.

The estimation process was carried out in detail and step by step. First, the data of each input between 1990 and 2023 was taken, and the following year, it was estimated with ES. In this process, the α value determined for each input data set was updated in each estimation year, and a stronger input estimation was obtained. The input estimation values of each year were substituted into the OLS equation, and the WL output value for the current year was obtained. In this way, the estimation was made up to 2040.

According to the results of the forward-looking estimation, the OTS Region closes the graphical difference with the EU Region in terms of WL considerably towards 2040. The OTS Region's reaching a good level of welfare brings many positive features, such as increasing income, improving the health system, increasing the use of clean energy, and making the region a centre of attraction. However, it should be noted that a country-based review can be considered in order to make more specific and detailed comments. In fact, in our study, the averages of five countries affiliated with the OTS are compared with the averages of five selected countries affiliated with the EU. Country-based WL analysis could be the subject of a separate study.

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